

RESEARCH PAPER

THE EFFECTS OF DROUGHT STRESS ON FLOWERING AND FRUIT FORMATION OF FIVE OKRA GENOTYPES IN SOUTH-WEST NIGERIA

C.O. Anyaoha*, U. Orkpeh and T. A. Fariyike
National Horticultural Research Institute, Idi-Ishin, PMB 5432, Ibadan, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The effects of drought stress on flowering time and fruit formation in okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L.) were investigated. Two landraces and three improved genotypes of okra were exposed to two distinct drought stress conditions (moderate and severe) and a normal watering regime. The experiment was laid out in completely randomized design with two replicates. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) indicated significant differences among the genotypes for some of the characters studied. The genotypes variously exhibited characteristic responses and useful traits that can be attributed to drought tolerance, including early flowering, late flowering, high chlorophyll content, and post-drought recovery. The variability in the timing of reproductive maturity as observed in this study strongly suggests earliness or delayed flowering as an efficient escape mechanisms in okra to mitigate the impact of drought on fruit production and, consequently, yield. All the varieties exhibited some ability to recover from drought damage after water was reapplied to previously stressed plants.

KEYWORDS: *Abelmoschus esculentus*, drought stress, flowering, pod setting

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Corresponding Author: kriskoty@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Vegetables generally constitute important components of our daily cuisine globally. They contain important food nutrients such as minerals and vitamins needed to build and repair the body (Bakhru, 2003). Okra is an important vegetable crop with high nutritional, medicinal and industrial values (Gopalan *et al.*, 2007). It was first domesticated in West and Central Africa but is now widely grown throughout the tropics mainly for dietary consumption. Several varieties abound and vary by height, fruit size and color, earliness, and response to photoperiod (Udoh *et al.*, 2005). The crop ranks first when compared to other vegetables in Nigeria (Babatunde *et al.*, 2007). Okra production constitutes about 4.6 percent of the total staple food production in Nigeria in the years 1970 to 2003 (CBN, 2004). The immature pods are boiled fresh as vegetables or used as soup thickeners. World production of okra is estimated at 600,000 tons per year while overall production in West Africa is estimated to be above 500,000 tons per year (Burkil, 1997). Despite the nutritional, economic and industrial importance of this vegetable, its optimum yields of (2 – 3 ton per ha) is yet to be achieved mainly in the tropics due to shortage of water and climate change (Ghanad *et al.*, 2014).

Drought is a condition in which soil moisture contents are too low or fixed for plant roots to absorb and meet the physiological and biochemical activities of the plant. Reduction in water supply during the growth and development of okra tend to lead to overall yield reduction mainly as time of first picking approaches (Yadev and Dhankhar,

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2002). Most morphological, physiological and biochemical processes associated with plant development are obstructed during drought stress thus resulting to poor photosynthesis, respiration, and overall crop yield.

Drought stress can occur at two main developmental stages of crop growth: early drought (seedling and developmental stage) and late drought (flowering and pod filling stage) (Seghatoleslami, *et al.* 2007; Kron *et al.* 2008). Plants respond and mitigate the adverse effects of drought using three main mechanisms such as earliness or escape, drought avoidance, drought tolerance and drought recovery (Turner, 1986; Kholodova *et al.* 2007). With the onset of climate change and its devastating effects mainly in west Africa, there is need to develop resilient high yielding okro varieties that can help our farmers to cushion the devastating economic effects associated with climate change such as drought, over flooding, high salinity, and low nutrient availability. The basic approach for development of drought tolerant genotypes is to screen and select locally adapted germplasm containing genetic variability for high yield potential and drought adaptive traits under stressed and unstressed environments (Beck *et al.*, 1990; Vasal *et al.*, 1997).

This work was carried out to screen five selected popular okro varieties for the effect of drought stress on their flowering and pod set in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Five okra genotypes – V35 (V1), *Benue* (V2), LD88 (V3), 47-4 (V4) and *Ibadan* (V5) – were used in this study. 47-4 and LD88 are improved varieties developed by National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT), Ibadan, Nigeria. V35 was developed by Institute for Agricultural Research and Training (IAR&T), Ibadan, while *Ibadan* and *Benue* are local farmers' varieties that are widely cultivated by okra farmers in Oyo and Benue states of Nigeria, respectively.

The experiment was carried out under screen house conditions at NIHORT in October 2014. Three seeds of okra were planted in perforated pots filled with dry sterilized sandy loam soil. Each pot weighed 3.1kg with dry soil and 3.5kg when watered optimally. The seedlings were thinned down to two stands per pot two weeks after germination. The five okra genotypes were laid out in a completely randomized design, replicated twice, and subjected to three water regimes (moderate draught stress – MS, severe draught stress – SS, and no draught stress control – NS). Plants in all three water regime sets received enough water thrice weekly until 30 days after sowing (DAS) when draught stress was initiated. In the MS set, water application was initially withdrawn for seven days, after which the plants were watered optimally on the eighth day before withdrawing water application again until complete leaf loss was observed in at least one variety. In the SS set, water application was withdrawn from 30 DAS until complete leaf loss due to draught at least one variety. Also the pots were randomly selected and weighed at three days interval to help estimate the level of water loss and stress in each trial. Water application was then resumed in both draught sets to assess the ability of each of the varieties to recover from drought.

Data collection

Data on the following parameters were obtained: plant height (PH, cm), leaf length (LL, cm), leaf cross section (LC, cm), petiole length (PL, cm), days to 50% flowering (DF), number of pods set (NP) and chlorophyll content (CC) using SPAD meter. Data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Genstatat Discovery Edition 4. Means and standard deviation were also determined at 5% level of probability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

V3 was generally observed to be the tallest variety, recording 37cm, 35cm and 44.2 cm under MS, SS and NS conditions, respectively. V2 was the shortest variety (Figures 1, 2 and 3). V4 had the longest leaves, while the shortest leaves were observed in V5 in the MS set. V1 exhibited the longest leaves under SS and NS conditions (Figures 1, 2 and 3). Chlorophyll content was highest in V5 across the three water regime sets, while the least SPAD readings were recorded for V2 in the MS set, V2 and V3 in the SS set, and for V3 in the NS control (Figures 1, 2 and 3).

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V2 was the first to attain 50% flowering under all three water regimes at 56 DAS. V5 only flowered under moderate stress and control at 61 DAS. V1, V3 and V4 did not flower at all under both stress conditions. In terms of fruit set, V2 produced two pods under severe stress, while the other four varieties did not produce any. In the MS set, V2 and V5 produced three pods each, V1 produced one pod, while V3 and V4 did not set pod. After water application was resumed to ascertain the recovery abilities of the varieties, V1 was the first to flower at 72DAS under moderate draught stress, while V5 flowered first at 77 DAS under severe draught stress. V2 and V4 were the last to flower under moderate and severe draught, respectively (Figures 1, 2 and 3).

The ANOVA revealed significant differences among the five okra genotypes for some of the parameters studied as regards their response to different water regimes (Table 1).

Drought stress is a major abiotic factor affecting crop yield. Plants are known to have evolved different physiological and biochemical mechanisms to overcome the effects and impacts of drought stress. The differences in flowering times and fruiting observed among the five okra varieties studied may likely be as a result of differences in the biochemical regulation and/or physiological pathways associated with plant growth under drought stress.

Reduction in water supply during the growth and development of okra tends to lead to overall yield reduction especially as time of first picking approaches (Yadev and Dhankhar, 2002). Most morphological, physiological and biochemical processes associated with plant development are obstructed during drought stress thus resulting in poor photosynthesis, respiration, and nutrient metabolism (Moniruzzaman, 2007; Naveed *et al.*, 2009). An efficient use of limited water resources and better growth under limited water supply are desirable traits for crops grown under drought prone environments. Plants respond to and mitigate the adverse effects of drought using any, or a combination, of the following mechanisms: earliness or escape, drought avoidance, drought tolerance and drought recovery (Turner, 1986; Kholodova *et al.*, 2007).

V2 is the earliest among the five genotypes and was able to produce flower and successfully set pods across the three water regimes but had poor recovery ability under severe drought stress. V1 exhibited the best recovery ability under moderate drought stress while V5 showed best recovery ability under the full stress condition by flowering 4 days earlier than V1 and V4.

V2 and V5 can be recommended to farmers living in areas with predictable short duration of rainfall since they were able to flower and produce pods under drought conditions apparently through an escape mechanism. On the other hand, V1 and V5 employed delay mechanism under moderate and severe drought stress respectively to mitigate the detrimental effects of drought by not flowering during the stress period until water was reapplied. These two varieties can thus be utilized as breeding material for development of okra genotypes suitable for planting in areas with a late rainfall pattern.

Hessini *et al.* (2009) reported that growth inhibition in terms of height; leaf area and number are the first major symptoms of drought stress in plant. This was also observed in almost all of the varieties used in this study, when compared to the control. Decrease in total biomass production can also be associated with decrease in leaf area leading to reduction in transpiration and overall photosynthetic activities. Jaleel *et al.* (2009) noted that development of optimal leaf area is important to photosynthesis and dry matter yield. This was in line with our current observation where V3 (that flowered last under both drought stress conditions) exhibited delayed flowering and recorded complete leaf loss in some plants as well as death of some plants, thus confirming their high susceptibility to drought stress. Decrease in plant height as noted in this study due to drought stress when compared with the control may be attributed to upset of some biochemical activities within the plant resulting to reduced cell division and elongation as also reported by Kusvuran *et al.*, 2008. Abd El-Kader *et al.* (2010) also observed that height and stem diameter of okra increased by enhancement of water availability. They reported that decrease in morphological characters like plant height occurred when the irrigation interval was increased.

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Understanding the genetic variability and response of these popular okra genotypes to drought stress will help to facilitate better planning and execution of okra genetic improvement programs in Nigeria. Such breeding programs can be geared towards development of resilient okra varieties that can help cushion the negative effects of climate change on poor resourced okra farmers.

Table 1. Statistical description and ANOVA of five okra genotypes

Characters	Mean	Min	Max	F-Value	SED
Plant height	33.3	28	44	<0.001	1.45
leaf length	8.7	5	13	0.122	1.39
leaf cross section	11.2	5	16.5	0.022	1.83
petiole length	5	2	8.7	0.309	1.185
SPAD	38.8	32.9	44.6	0.135	2.166
Days to 50% flowering	78.1	78.1	84	0.039	15.23
Days to flowering after rewatering	72	72	84	0.499	2.75

Figure 1. Response of five okra genotypes to moderate stress

Figure 2. Response of five okro genotypes to severe stress

Figure 3. Response of five okro genotypes under optimal water regime (No water stress)

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